

A Flexible OMV-based Platform for Oral Vaccination in Aquaculture

Vaccination is the most effective strategy to control infectious diseases in aquaculture, improving welfare, reducing antibiotic use and limiting economic losses. However, **current approaches have limitations.** Injectable vaccines require handling and sedation, increasing labour and stress, are not suitable for small fish, and often rely on adjuvants associated with undesirable side effects. Immersion vaccines are less invasive but may provide weaker or shorter protection. **Oral vaccination is an attractive alternative,** yet its effectiveness is **often limited by antigen degradation in the gastrointestinal tract and insufficient immune stimulation.**

To unlock the full potential of oral vaccination, new approaches must ensure antigen stability and strong immune activation without compromising safety or practicality.

IGNITION is developing a vaccination platform based on outer membrane vesicles (OMVs). These nanovesicles, which are naturally secreted by **Gram-negative bacteria, act as intrinsic immune stimulators and can be engineered to carry antigens from different pathogens.** In this project, **OMVs derived from *Photobacterium damsela* subsp. *piscicida* (Phdp) are being optimised for safety and immunostimulatory properties and used to incorporate heterologous antigens, enabling multivalent vaccine development.**

This approach positions Phdp OMVs as a **safe and adaptable backbone for vaccine development**, opening new opportunities for developing oral and feed-based immunisation strategies that reduce

handling and vaccination stress. **Preliminary results from IGNITION confirm the feasibility and potential of this OMV-based platform.**

Detoxified OMVs induce strong systemic and mucosal IgM responses without added adjuvant

European sea bass intraperitoneally injected with optimised (detoxified) OMVs from Phdp without added adjuvant developed **significant systemic (serum) and mucosal (gut mucus) antigen-specific IgM responses**,

demonstrating that **engineered OMVs retain intrinsic immunostimulatory properties and can function as self-adjuvanted vaccine carriers**.

A single OMV-based platform for developing multivalent vaccines

Loading OMVs with antigens from different pathogens **did not alter vesicle morphology or size distribution**, confirming structural stability after antigen incorporation.

These results support the use of **engineered OMVs as a flexible platform for multivalent vaccine development**, enabling the **combination of multiple disease targets within a single system**.

Efficient intestinal delivery of OMV-derived antigens supports oral vaccination potential

Following oral administration, **OMV-derived antigens were detected** by immunohistochemistry (brown colour) **in the distal intestine of European sea bass and rainbow trout**. The uptake of the antigens after

gastrointestinal transit **supports the potential use of these OMVs in oral vaccination strategies, including feed-based delivery**.

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